

Role of Information Technology in Banking Sector

G.Jeyachitra, M.Com., M.Phil.,
Assistant Professor

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Jeyachitra, G. "Role of Information Technology in Banking Sector." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 76–81.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595722>

Abstract

Liberalization and Information technology has attracted many foreign banks to India, thereby opening up new markets, new products and efficient delivery channels for the banking industry. In the development of Indian economy. Banking sector plays a very important and crucial role. With the use of technology there had been an increase in penetration, productivity and efficiency. It has not only increased the cost effectiveness but also has helped in making small value transactions viable. Commercial Banks in India are now becoming a one-stop Supermarket. The focus is shifting from mass banking to class banking with the introduction of value added and customized products. Technology allows banks to create what looks like a branch in a business building's lobby without having to hire manpower for manual operations. The branches are running on the concept of 24 X 7 working, made possible by the use of Tele banking, ATMs, Internet banking, Mobile banking and E – banking technology driven delivery channels are being used to reach out to maximum number of customers at lower cost and in more efficient manner. The beauty of these banking innovations is that it puts both banker and customer in a win- win situation. Effective use of technology has a multiplier effect on growth and development.

Introduction

The term "Banking Technology" refers to the use of sophisticated information and communication technologies. This activities Successful use of data mining help the banks to achieve significant increase in profits and thereby retain sustainable advantage over their competitors. From theoretical perspective, Banking Technology is not a single, stand-alone discipline, but a confluence of several disparate fields such as finance (subsuming risk management), information technology, communication technology, computer science and marketing science. The use of appropriate hardware for conducting business and servicing the customers through various delivery channels and payments systems and the associated software constitutes one dimension of Banking Technology. The use of computer networks, security algorithms in its transactions, use of ATM and credit cards, Internet banking, telebanking and mobile banking are all covered by this dimension. The advances made in information and communication technologies take care of this dimension. Moreover, banks cannot ignore the risks that arise in conducting business with other banks and servicing their customers, for otherwise, their very existence would be at stake. Thus, the

quantification, measurement, mitigation and management of all the kinds of risks that banks face constitutes the third important dimension of Banking Technology. This dimension covers the process of measuring and managing credit risk, market risk and operational risk.

History of Indian Banking Sector

The Government of India initiated that banks play an vital role in the economic roadmap of the nation, the Indian government was adopted the mixed economy in 1948. Indian Government took big decision concerning the Indian Banking Sector Reform after independence. Firstly, Indian government transformed Imperial Bank of India converted into a nationalized bank and it became the state bank of India with extensive banking facilities on a large scale especially in rural and semi urban areas. Government of India took many banking initiatives. These were aimed to provide banking coverage to all section of the society and every sector of the economy.

Review of Literature

Shastri R.V, (March, 2003) “Recent trends in Banking Industry-IT emergence, Chartered Financial Analyst, (pp 45-56) in this article stated that liberalization policy and intense competition keeps every banker on his toes. Implementation of Information Technology (IT) helps for maintaining proper accounts especially in decision making process. He also stated that facilities like ATM, anywhere banking, Internet and mobile banking have imported customer service which in turn helps for better customer relations management. He also explained the challenges faced by banks because of IT implementation like employment problem and security concerns. He suggested that the customer delight is the primary goal of all future IT initiatives. Prabhakar Rao Ch. (Jan, 2004). —Indian banking in 2010-IBA Bulletin Special Issues, (pp 170-173) in this study discussed about the revolutionary changes that witnessed in the financial sector around the world. He stated that net worked branches. ATMs, technology based payment and settlement system, technology vision of RBI, floating rate of interest have changed the Indian banking sector. He concluded that brick and mortar bank branches will disappear and customers will be able to operation their accounts through electronic devices.

Objectives of the Study

The main Objective of this research paper is to review the implementation of IT in Banking Industry. Technological innovations have enabled the industry to open up new delivery channels, seeking the help of IT to deal with the challenges that a new economy poses.

1. To study the rapid advancement occurring in the banking sector.
2. To analyses the performance of existing technology based on products offered by the banks in India and its future prospects.
3. To determine the extent to which information technology has contributed to customer satisfaction and banks performance.

Banking Technology in Indian Banking

The Indian banking sector consists of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), which is the central bank, commercial banks and co-operative banks. Commercial banks are of two types – scheduled, which are subject to statutory requirements and non-scheduled, which are not. Scheduled banks can be further classified into public sector banks [comprising of the State bank of India, its seven associates, other nationalized banks and the Regional Rural Banks (RRBs)] and private sector banks, which can be either domestic or foreign. The Indian Banking Industry has

Information Technology Considerations

Since the early nineties, each Indian bank has done some IT improvement effort. The first and foremost compulsion is the fierce competition. While deciding on the required architecture for the IT consideration is given to following realities.

1. Meeting Internal Requirement: The requirements of the banks are different individually depending upon their nature and volume of business; focus on a particular segment, spread of branches and a like. Many a time's banks do have the required information but it is scattered. The operating units seldom know the purpose of gathering the information by their higher authorities.
2. Effective in Data Handling: As stated earlier the banks have most of the needed data but are distributed. Further the cost of collection of data and putting the same to use is prohibitively high. The accuracy and timeliness of data generation becomes the causalities in the process. Best of the intentions on computerization are wished away because there is nonvisible reduction in cost/efforts/time required for the required data gathering.
3. Extending Customer Services: Addressing to rising customers expectations is significant particularly in the background of increased competition. In case bank A is unable to provide the required service at a competitive price and in an accurate manner with speed. There is always a bank IT at its next-door waiting to hire the customer. Awareness of customers about the availability of services and their pricing as also available options have brought into sharp focus the issue of customer satisfaction.
4. Creative Support for New Product Development: It has become necessary for the banks to vitalize the process of product development. Marketing functionaries needs a lot of information not only from the outside sources but also from within the banks. Banks are looking to retail segment as the future market places for sales efforts. Having full-fledged information of existing customer is the key for this purpose. The emergences of data requirement and an appropriate architecture to support the same are significant issues to be handled in this regard.
5. End-user Development of the Non-technical Staff: Banking being a service industry, it is he staffs at counters that deliver the products. In Indian scenario, virtual banking is likely to have a few more years to establish. The dependence on counter staff is unavoidable. The staffs are large in number and the majority is non-technical. The customer satisfaction levels at the counter determine the ultimate benefit of IT offensive. Giving due consideration to this aspect in choosing architecture is necessary.

Nationalization Process

First phase of Indian Banks nationalization process was in 1969. The major objective of nationalization process was to extend banking infrastructure in rural areas. Fourteen banks were nationalized in 1969. Before 1969, State Bank of India (SBI) was only the public sector bank in India. And second phase of Indian banks nationalization process was in 1980. Seven more banks were nationalized with deposits over 200 crores. Currently 20 public sector banks, 21 private sector banks and 43 foreign banks are working in India.

Recent Developments in Banking Sector

1. Electronic-cheques

Electronic cheques works same as paper cheques but payment transaction can be done through digital format. XML document provide mechanism to authenticate parties to make transactions. In e-cheques signatures are accompanied by bank –issued certificates which tie with signer's key to bank account. Nowadays it is very commonly using by everyone .many of transferring amount

transaction can be done through electronic cheques. E-cheques make easy transfer of payments to customers which are easily available to make payment for online purchases. It reduces chance to cheque bouncing banks always give awareness about their account details when any transaction can be done.

2. Internet

Internet is a networking of computers. In this marketing message can be transferred and received worldwide. The data can be sent and received in any part of the world. In no time, internet facility can do many a job for us. It includes the following: This net can work as electronic mailing system.

- It can have access to the distant database, which may be a newspaper of foreign country. We can exchange our ideas through Internet. We can make contact with anyone who is a linked with internet. On internet, we can exchange letters, figures/diagrams and music recording.
- Internet is a fast developing net and is of utmost important for public sector undertaking, Education Institutions, Research Organization etc.

3. Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

ATM is an electronic machine, which is Recent Developments in Banking Sector (1.) Internet: Internet is a networking of computers. In this marketing message can be transferred and received worldwide. The data can be sent and received in any part of the world. In no time, internet facility can do many a job for us. It includes the following: This net can work as electronic mailing system

- It can have access to the distant database, which may be a newspaper of foreign country. We can exchange our ideas through Internet. We can make contact with anyone
- On internet, we can exchange letters, figures/diagrams and music recording
- Internet is a fast developing net and is of utmost important for public sector undertaking, Education Institutions, Research Organization etc.

Electronic Fund Transfer

The EFT system enables an account holder of a bank to electronically transfer funds to another account holder with any other bank..The most widely used EFT programs is Direct deposits, in which payroll is deposited straight into an employee's bank account, although it transfer the funds through an electronic terminal including Credit card, ATM and Point of Sales (POS) transactions.

National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT)

The EFT system enables an account holder of a bank to electronically transfer funds to another account holder with any other bank..The most widely used EFT programs is Direct deposits, in which payroll is deposited straight into an employee's bank account, although it transfer the funds through an electronic terminal including Credit card, ATM and Point of Sales (POS) transactions.

New and improved variant of EFT was implemented in November 2005 to facilitate one to one fund transfer requirement of individuals as well as corporate. It uses the Structured Financial Messaging Solution (SFMS) for EFT message creation and transmission from the branch to the banks gateway and to the NEFT centre, so it can transfer the funds with more security. With the SFMS facility, branches can participate in both RTGS and NEFT System. Using the NEFT infrastructure, a one-way remittance facility from India to Nepal has also been implemented by the RBI since 15th May, 2008. Overall EFT and NEFT based clearing increased from Rs.394.1 million to Rs.927.6 million in year 2012-2013 to 2014-2015

Real Time Gross Settlements (RTGS)

The introduction of RTGS in 2004 was instrumental in the development of infrastructure for Systematically Important Payment System (SIPS) and it settles all interbank payments and customer transactions above 2 Lakhs. RTGS was launched by RBI, which enabled a real time settlement on a gross basis. To ensure that RTGS system is used only for large value transactions and retail transactions take an alternate channel of EFT. The reach and utilization of RTGS has witnessed a sustain-able increase since its introduction. In the year 2012-2013 to 2014-2015 transactions related to customer remittances have raised from Rs.68.5 million to Rs.92.8 million. This shows the increasing popularity of RTGS in Indian banking industry.

Society for Worldwide Inter-Bank Financial Telecommunications (Swift)

SWIFT, as a co-operative society was formed in May 1973 with 239 participating banks from 15 countries with its headquarters at Brussels. It started functioning in May 1977. RBI and 27 other public sector banks as well as 8 foreign banks in India have obtained the membership of the SWIFT. SWIFT provides have rapid, secure, reliable and cost effective mode of transmitting the financial messages worldwide. At present more than 3000 banks are the members of the network. To cater to the growth in messages, SWIFT was upgrade in the 80s and this version is called SWIFT-II. Banks in India are hooked to SWIFT-II system. SWIFT is a method of the sophisticated message transmission of international repute. This is highly cost effective, reliable and safe means of fund transfer. This network also facilitates the transfer of messages relating to fixed deposit, interest rates also.

- Payment, debit-credit statements, foreign exchange etc. This service is available throughout the year, 24 hours a day.
- This system ensure against any loss of mutilation against transmission
- It serves almost all financial institution and selected range of other users
- 7 www.ssijmar.in It is clear from the above benefit of SWIFT that it is very beneficial in effective customer service. SWIFT has extended its range to users like brokers, trust and other agents.

Conclusion

The mobile and wireless market has been one of the fastest growing markets in the world. The arrival of technology and the escalating use of mobile and smart phone devices, has given the banking industry new platform. Connecting a customer anytime and anywhere to their money and needs is a must have service that has become an unstoppable necessity. This is worldwide communication is leading a new generation of strong banking relationship. The banking world can achieve superior interactions with their public base if they accommodate all their customer needs. They have a unique challenge to keep their customer alliances and keeping up with the new technologies, and competitive strategies that other banks also have to offer the public. Conveniences of services plus outside locations like ATMS are crucial to every banks success. Meeting all challenges including safety and security are perfect examples of good banking strategies. In order for the financial institutions to effectively grow they must embrace the new technologies and customize them to suit their economic success and the public success. Online banking is certainly here to stay. As a tool of modern living and as almost impossible to conveniently with regular banking. As we venture in to the future, the internet will undoubtedly continue to change the banking industry.

References

1. Dhingra Sanjay,2011, Measuring IT Effectiveness in Banks of India for Sustainable Development ,BVICAM's International Journal of Information Technology, pp-347-350.
2. <http://www.banknetindia.com/special/itbanking.htm>.
3. <http://www.britannica.com/bps>.
4. <http://findarticles.com>
5. <http://highbeam.com>.
6. Jain M. &.Popli G.S., Role of Information Technology in the development of Banking Sector in India.
7. RBI Annual Report
8. Sharma M.C. Role of Information Technology in Indian Banking Sector, SHIV SHAKTI, International Journal in Multidisciplinary and Academic Research, Vol. 2, No. 1,PP-1-12.